

Overall Customer Satisfaction: Impact on Online Reviews on Students' Purchasing Decision

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ABSTRACT

During the pandemic, the majority of customers shop online. Customers are more inclined to buy from a website with user-verified reviews. Displaying reviews on your website instills trust in the consumers to purchase and eliminates uncertainty, resulting in a greater conversion rate. Online reviews are valuable tools for maintaining good and positive customer feedback. It also helps the customers to identify if the products have low quality or will attain their satisfaction. This study sought to determine the impact of online reviews on students' purchasing decisions to attain overall customer satisfaction. The study was also deemed significant to the students, online businesses, other consumers, and future researchers. The researchers use a quantitative approach and a correlation research design to investigate the relationship between the factors of online reviews and their impact on students' purchasing decisions. The data was gathered through survey questionnaires and distributed to the sample of 62 Business Administration First to Fourth-year students of Bulacan State University - Meneses Campus. The data analysis uses frequency, mean, standard deviation, tables, and charts. In the characteristics of online reviews, customers' experience got the highest overall mean of 3.62.

In contrast, product quality is the highest factor affecting the students' purchasing decisions, with an overall mean of 3.56. The Pearson correlation proved a moderate positive relationship between the variables, where the result is $r=0.617$ with a $p\text{-value}=0.000$. The outcome helped in rejecting the null hypothesis. In addition, the researchers concluded that online reviews impact students' purchasing decisions to attain overall customer satisfaction.

Keywords: *Customer satisfaction, Online reviews, Students, Purchasing decision, Impact*

INTRODUCTION

Online reviews are so common in today's consumer landscape that they are nearly impossible to avoid. Online businesses provide online reviews as an alternative to customers interacting with a product to increase their confidence (Changchit et al., 2022). Almost every business today has a social media presence, and most have a website with active engagement that includes review sections. Online review is significant for consumers; it builds their trust in a specific product they will purchase. From the reviews, purchasers are educated about the product's quality, the shipping rate, the efficiency of refundable or exchangeable terms, the past customer's review, the variety of options, and the incoming new product. In addition, recommendations and all the aspects that they read can affect their purchasing decisions. Consumers regard online customer reviews, whether positive or negative, as valuable sources of information (Cheng & Ho, 2015). Positive reviews can convince consumers to eliminate doubts and be confident in their decisions. While on the other hand, negative reviews lessen the consumers' trust. Customers frequently rely on online product reviews to assess their products' quality, which significantly impacts their purchasing decision (Zhong et al., 2021). Online reviews are a type of online reputation management (Guan et al., 2017). Online customer reviews are increasingly important in other customers' decision-making processes (Grover & Goyal, 2020). They will avoid the

poorly reviewed product and choose among the best. Students considered online reviews in their purchasing decisions. Their income is still in the highs and lows, so they are still dependent on their allowances and sidelines. They are more on proper budgeting and good spending habits. They want to find reliable and accurate reviews based on other people's or strangers' online experiences. Written reviews with a high star rating are four of 4the most helpful guides to their effective decisions. Moreover, they feel satisfied if what they perceive is what they receive at the end of their purchasing journey.

The most challenging question facing today's corporate executives and small online business owners is: How impactful are online reviews? How will students remain satisfied like the other consumers? Therefore, the study would explore the role of online reviews in students' purchasing decisions, considering their credibility, trustworthiness, helpfulness, and customers' experience, which could differ from the general consumer population.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. Research design is the overall strategy used to effectively utilize and analyze the research study to answer the research problems. The researchers will use a Quantitative Approach. It is an approach used to collect and study numerical data collected from the survey questionnaires that the researchers will disseminate to the target respondent of the study. Under the quantitative approach, the researchers will use a correlation research design to investigate the relationship between the factors of online reviews and their impact on students' purchasing decisions. The primary data source is collected from the responses among Business Administration students from Bulacan State University Meneses Campus that purchases products online. The study aims to answer and analyze the factors of online reviews that impact students' purchasing decisions.

Participants/Respondents. The study used simple random sampling to include 62 students from the population of Business Administration students at Bulacan State University Meneses Campus. It is a type of probability sampling in which the researchers randomly select a subset of participants from a population in which they have an equal chance of being selected to avoid unbiased data. The sample was identified through the use of a Raosoft calculator. The researchers applied a 10% margin of error and a 90% confidence level.

Data Collection Procedure. The data gathering was conducted online through the use of Google Forms. The Business Administration students of Bulacan State University Meneses Campus were the target respondents of the study. The respondents received a link to the survey questionnaire. The researchers will thank the respondents for actively participating during the data collection.

Data Analysis Procedure. The data gathered from the questionnaire were computed using Minitab19, Statistical Software. Part I, it is about the profile of the respondents. The tables showed the frequency and percentages of the data. Also, charts were used to organize and describe the respondents' personal information.

For Part II, Mean and Standard Deviation were presented to analyze the factors relating to the characteristics of Online Reviews. Tables were used to elaborate on the data.

The following scale was utilized for verbal interpretation:

Scale	Range	Response Category
4	3.26 – 4.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.51 – 3.25	Agree
2	1.76 – 2.50	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.75	Strongly Disagree

Part III presents the factors that can affect the Students' Purchasing Decisions. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to determine the viability of the data presented and followed by its verbal description. Tables were used to elaborate on the data.

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For Part IV, Pearson Correlation was used to examine the hypothesis at a 10% significance level. This determines if a positive or negative relationship exists between Online Reviews and Students' Purchasing Decisions to attain Overall Customer Satisfaction. To determine the results, the researchers used the formula.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data Analysis

As stated, 62 survey questionnaires were answered online by the Business Administration students to assess the impact of Online Reviews on Students' Purchasing Decisions to attain Overall Customer Satisfaction. All the obtained data are compiled using the data spreadsheets. Moreover, the data was presented and analyzed using tables and charts.

Part I - Respondents' Profile

Part I contains the respondent's profile, including information on their gender, age, and status.

Part IV – Pearson Correlation

Figure 5

In the figure above, the Pearson correlation between online reviews and students' purchasing decision is about 0.617, indicating a moderate positive relationship between the variables. Furthermore, it reveals that the $p\text{-value} = 0.000 < 0.10$ level of significance; thus, the null hypothesis that online reviews have no impact on students' purchasing decisions to attain overall customer satisfaction was rejected. Therefore, the statistical analysis concludes that online reviews impact students' purchasing decisions to attain overall customer satisfaction.

Online shopping has been the new trend of purchasing products for consumers during the pandemic, wherein it is more effective and efficient. Online reviews on social media platforms significantly impact consumers, especially students' purchasing decisions (Chen et al., Q. (2011). It is the driving force that dictates and decides whether to purchase a particular product or not based on the feedback from other consumers shared through different online platforms.

The study discussed different factors under online reviews; these are the credibility in which respondents strongly agree that online reviews are credible if it is from verified buyers (Zhu et al., 2010). The second factor is trustworthiness, in which respondents strongly agree that they always explore online reviews to determine the genuine ones (Fileri, R.,2016). The third factor is helpfulness; if an online review is well-written, it contributes to their purchasing decision (Chen et al., 2011). The last factor under online reviews is the customers' experience; it is stated that respondents strongly agree that a positive buying experience leads to good online reviews (Chevalier et al., 2016). The presented factors can therefore conclude that customers' experience has the most significant impact on students' purchasing decisions, with a mean of 3.62 and a verbal description of strongly agree. For the factors under students' purchasing decision, first on the list is the intention; respondents strongly agree that they consider their financial condition when purchasing a product and thoroughly read online reviews to make an effective purchasing decision. The second factor is the brand reputation; respondents

strongly agree that the recommendation of other people can affect their views on the brand's reputation. Third is product quality; respondents stated that they tend to focus on the quality of the product, which impacts their purchasing decision. Last on the list of factors under students' purchasing decisions is the marketing strategies; respondents strongly agree that discounts and free shipping offers can increase their purchasing powers.

Therefore, the presented factors under students' purchasing decisions can conclude that product quality, with an overall mean of 3.56 and a verbal description of, strongly agree the critical aspect that can affect students' purchasing decision to buy a particular product. As a clear result, it showed that online reviews impact the students' purchasing decisions that help to achieve overall customer satisfaction, which rejects the null hypothesis.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings above, most respondents were female, indicating a gender imbalance in the sample. Furthermore, the group aged 20 represented the highest percentage of participants, suggesting that this age group was most interested or accessible for the study. When considering the respondents' status, it was observed that the majority were full-time students. This information provides insights into the demographics of the study participants and highlights the need for further research to ensure a more balanced representation across gender and age. The factors contributing to online reviews were credibility, trustworthiness, helpfulness, and customer experience. These factors played a crucial role in enabling respondents to evaluate the positive attributes of online reviews. The respondents strongly agreed that customer experience ranked highest among these factors and significantly impacted students' purchasing decisions. This finding emphasizes the influence of online reviews on consumers' choices, particularly among students.

Regarding students' purchasing decisions, several factors were identified as influential, including intention, brand reputation, product quality, and marketing strategies. The respondents strongly agreed that product quality emerged as a critical aspect affecting their purchase of a particular product. This highlights the importance of ensuring high-quality offerings to attract student consumers. Moreover, the findings indicated a moderate positive relationship between online reviews and students' purchasing decisions, ultimately leading to overall customer satisfaction. It is worth noting that the positive responses and data collected from the 1st to 4th-year Business Administration students significantly contributed to the study's successful outcome. These findings shed light on this specific group's preferences and decision-making processes, providing valuable insights for businesses and marketers targeting student consumers. However, further research with a more diverse sample is necessary to generalize the results and comprehensively understand the topic.

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